

ULTRASONIC WELDING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES. MODELING THE HEATING PHENOMENA.

A. Levy¹, I. Fernandez Villegas^{2,*}, S. Le Corre³

¹Structures and Composites Materials Laboratory, McGill University, 817 Sherbrooke St. West, Montreal, Quebec, Canada H3A 2K6

²Structural Integrity and Composites, Delft University of Technology, Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS Delft, The Netherlands

³Laboratoire de Thermocinétique de Nantes, La Chantrerie, rue Christian Pauc, BP 50609, 44306 Nantes cedex 3, France.

*Corresponding author (I.FernandezVillegas@tudelft.nl)

1 Introduction

Thermoplastic composites offer new possibilities for the aerospace industry. Huge structures (several meters) can be processed rapidly and more cost-effectively than when thermoset composites are used, since the latter need to undergo lengthy curing reactions. The ability to fuse thermoplastic resins gives new perspectives for processing and assembling. Fusion bonding, usually known as welding is, indeed, a group of joining techniques specific to thermoplastic composites that offers a very interesting alternative to traditional assembling via adhesive bonding or mechanical fastening.

Within this group, ultrasonic welding of thermoplastic composites is based on low-amplitude and high-frequency vibrations that cause surface friction and viscoelastic heating at the welding interface. Its main advantages are very high speed (welding times of a few seconds) and the fact that no foreign material, such as a metal mesh or metal particles, is needed at the interface regardless the nature of the adherents. As first introduced by Fernandez Villegas [1], localized heating in ultrasonic welding of thermoplastic composites can be achieved by placing a film of neat matrix at the welding interface (Figure 1). This straightforward “flat energy director” solution contrasts with more traditional and complex energy directors derived from the plastics industry consisting of neat resin protrusions molded on the surfaces to be welded [2]. Flat energy directors concentrate heat dissipation at the welding interface as a result of their lower stiffness

Figure 1: Principle of the ultrasonic welding.

and hence their higher cyclic strain as compared to that of the composite adherents. Since they cover the whole overlap, they provide 100% welded areas without the need for any shape or size optimization.

The experimental work in Fernandez Villegas [1] coupled with the work of Zhang et al. [3] on heating of rectangular energy directors give a relevant insight into the different heating mechanisms and their roles in the ultrasonic process. Further work is however needed to fully understand the phenomena taking place in the flat-energy-director ultrasonic welding process. Of particular importance is the temperature developed at the welding interface and the extension of the heat affected zone (HAZ) in the adherents, which are difficult to measure by using thermography or traditional thermocouples. With this purpose, a multiphysical model was built and solved in COMSOL Multiphysics in order to simulate the heating mechanisms in the process. This model together with an experimental validation of the results they provide are presented in this paper.

Figure 2: Thermal conductivity of the CF/PEI composite and the neat PEI matrix.

2 Experimental methods

2.1 Material

The material used for this research is T300 carbon-fiber reinforced polyetherimide (CF/PEI) provided by Ten Cate Advanced Composites, The Netherlands.

PEI. The transverse k_{zz} and in-plane k_{xx} thermal conductivity of the composite and that of the neat PEI matrix k were measured by DSM using a nanoflash method and are plot versus temperature on figure 2. Despite the slight thermodependency one can observe in those graphs, we retain constant values for the modeling:

$$\begin{aligned} k_{xx} &= 0.61 \text{ W/mK} \\ k_{zz} &= 2.8 \text{ W/mK} \\ k &= 0.25 \text{ W/mK} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The specific heat capacity c_{PEI} of the neat PEI matrix was measured at TU Delft by using a Perkin-Elmer DSC 7 Differential Scanning Calorimeter. Its density ρ_{PEI} was measured by the manufacturer Sabic Innovative Plastics using a PVT apparatus. As shown on figure 3 the volumetric heat capacity of the PEI $\rho_{PEI}c_{PEI}$ is supposed to be linear versus temperature:

$$\rho_{PEI}c_{PEI} = 4110 \times T [^{\circ}\text{C}] + 1.24 \times 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3\cdot\text{K}. \quad (2)$$

The mechanical behavior of PEI is studied in appendix B.

Figure 3: volumetric Heat capacity of the neat PEI matrix $\rho_{PEI}c_{PEI}$ versus temperature.

Composite. The specific heat capacity c_{comp} of the CF/PEI composite was measured with the DSC. Considering a constant density $\rho_{CF} = 1760 \text{ kg/m}^3$ for the T300 carbon fiber and ρ_{PEI} above, the mixture rule allows to determine the density of the composite ρ_{comp} . The volumetric heat capacity is plotted versus temperature on figure 4. It is in good agreement with the volumetric heat capacity obtained using the mixtures rule:

$$\rho_{comp}c_{comp} = v_f(\rho_{CF}c_{CF}) + (1 - v_f)(\rho_{PEI}c_{PEI}) \quad (3)$$

where $v_f = 50\%$ is the fiber fraction, and $c_{CF} = 800 \text{ J/kg}\cdot\text{K}$ the T300 carbon fiber specific heat. Finally, the following linear dependence on temperature is assumed:

$$\rho_{comp}c_{comp} = 2700 \times T [^{\circ}\text{C}] + 1.3 \times 10^6 \text{ J/m}^3\cdot\text{K}. \quad (4)$$

The in-plane elastic modulus in the warp and weft directions was found by the manufacturer to vary very little (less than 3%). Moreover it is rather constant (within 5%) between 23°C and 80°C . For our quasi-isotropic composite, we pertain an in-plan elastic modulus:

$$E_{plan} = 55 \text{ GPa}. \quad (5)$$

It is considered constant on the whole process temperature range. On the contrary, the transverse modulus E_{zz} is obtained

The Poisson ratio of the composite is supposed isotropic and equal to 0.4.

Figure 4: Heat capacity of the CF/PEI composite c_{comp} versus temperature.

2.2 Processing

Six layers of five-harness satin CF reinforced prepreg were used to manufacture the base laminates in a hot platen press. The stacking sequence of the laminates was $[0/90]_{3s}$ and the manufacturing conditions were 20 minutes at 320°C and 20 bar. The nominal thickness of the consolidated laminates was 1.92 mm.

Rectangular samples ($101.6\text{ mm} \times 25.4\text{ mm}$) were cut out of the CF/PEI laminates with an abrasive saw so that the longer side of the samples coincided with the main apparent orientation of the fibers. These samples were degreased and welded in near-field [2] into a single-lap configuration with an overlap area of $12.7\text{ mm} \times 25.4\text{ mm}$ (according to ASTM D 1002). A film 0.25 mm thick PEI film is used as a flat energy director.

For the welding of the samples a 20kHz Rinco Dynamic 3000 ultrasonic welder with a maximum power input of 3000 W was used. The processing parameters relevant to the analysis in this paper were 500 N welding force and $86.2\ \mu\text{m}$ vibration amplitude. More detail on the experimental method can be found in Fernandez Villegas [1]. The ultrasonic welder provides feedback on the power dissipated during the process and the displacement of the sonotrode. The dissipated power, as well as the transformations undergone by the energy director in the different phases of the process as described in Fernandez Villegas [1], was used

for the validation of the COMSOL model.

3 Modeling

In this section, a modeling of the heating phenomena that allows to perform ultrasonic welding is proposed. Many authors studied the classical case where triangular shape energy directors are used. Tolunay et al. [4] suggested that the heating is solely due to mechanical dissipation of work through visco-elastic deformation. This suggested phenomenon has been widely assumed in the literature [5, 6] and allowed to perform analysis of industrial energy director shapes [7, 8]. More recently, Levy et al. [9] confirmed the heating term due to visco-elastic work dissipation using time homogenization technique based on asymptotic expansion. An integrated finite element code solving for the vibration, the heat transfer and the flow was developed [10, 11].

In the present study, because the energy director is not triangular but a film at the interface, new phenomena are occurring. The heating mechanism, as suggested by Zhang et al. [3] and Fernandez Villegas [1] also consists in frictional dissipation at the interface.

3.1 General macroscopic framework

Because of the sample geometry, a plane strain assumption is pertained and a two dimensional framework allows to describe the problem using three domains, as shown on figure 1. Using symmetries, only a quarter of the domain is considered.

In the present study, we propose to model the heating phase during ultrasonic welding with film energy directors. The framework is that of Levy et al. [10] except that we do not account for the flow, that mostly occurs in the subsequent phases of the process [1].

The physics solved are therefore:

- An elastic problem that describes the vibration effect. The boundary condition being a sinusoidal displacement imposed by the tool $u = a \sin(\omega t)$. As noticed by Levy et al. [11], this approach neglects the hammering effect brought up by Tolunay et al. [4] and considers contact between the sonotrode and the top composite. In

this study, we will consider that the contact between the sonotrode and the composite assembly is lost during a part of the cycle.

- A heat transfer problem that describes temperature evolution in the setup. Following existing works [4, 5, 6, 8, 3, 10], the viscoelastic dissipation appears as a thermal source of the form:

$$\dot{Q}_{bulk}(x,y) = \frac{\alpha_h^2 \omega E'' \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*}{2} \quad (6)$$

E'' being the loss modulus of the material and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*(x,y)$ the amplitude strain tensor obtained by solving one static elastic problem with the amplitude of vibration as a load. Because of the hammering effect, during an ultrasonic cycle, contact is lost between the sonotrode and the sample. This is accounted by introducing the efficiency coefficient α_h . If no hammering occurs, $\alpha_h = 1$ and the classical dissipation term from the literature is recovered. In the case of hammering, the sinusoidal strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* \sin(\omega t)$ occurs only during a fraction of the cycle, leading to a reduced viscoelastic dissipation. The data obtained with the normalized problem will be denoted with a star hereunder. Using the complex viscosity $\bar{\eta} = \eta' + i\eta'' = \bar{E}/i\omega$ instead (\bar{E} being the complex viscoelastic modulus), one can write

$$\dot{Q}_{bulk}(x,y) = \frac{\alpha_h^2 \omega^2 \eta' \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*}{2}. \quad (7)$$

It explicitly shows the quadratic dependency of the viscous dissipated power on the vibration frequency.

In addition to those bulk phenomena that have been treated in the literature, this study brings a special focus on the interfacial thermo-mechanical phenomena which are of particular importance in this process.

3.2 Microscopic analysis at the interface

In the following we call “interfaces” the lower and upper interface between the film and the lower, successively upper, composite plate.

First the friction phenomenon cannot be neglected, and induce an interfacial heat source. Then the contact

evolution at the microscopic scale is modeled using an intimate contact model. Finally the roughness at the interface, inherently linked to the intimate contact, acts as microscopic energy concentrator.

3.2.1 Friction

Because the stiffness of the neat matrix film at the interface is lower than that of the composite plates, its longitudinal deformation will be larger than that of the composite resulting in slippage and friction at the interfaces, and a displacement difference. In order to simulate this displacement discontinuity, a special connector was added at the interfaces between the plates and the film. A “thin elastic film”, as defined in COMSOL, was considered with the following anisotropic properties:

- A very high normal stiffness $K_n = 10^{18} \text{ N/m}^3$ constrains the normal displacement to be continuous, thus allowing a contact condition.
- An initial very low tangential stiffness $K_t^0 \sim 0$ simulates a perfect slip with no friction. This first model neglects the effect of friction on the deformation and therefore probably over-estimates the slippage. This simple “perfect slip” approach allows one to keep a linear elastic problem. Thus allowing to describe the sinusoidal response to the sinusoidal load by solving one single static problem (as discussed in section 3.1). Note that as adhesion occurs at the interface, the tangential stiffness K_t increases. We finally suppose an empirical quadratic dependency of K_t on the degree of adhesion D_a defined hereunder (section 3.2.3):

$$K_t = \frac{E_{zz}}{h} (2 \times 10^{-3} + D_a^2). \quad (8)$$

When D_a reaches 1, full sticking occurs and K_t reaches the very high value of E_{zz}/h where $h = 2 \mu\text{m}$ is a very thin equivalent layer thickness ($\sim 1\%$ of the film’s height).

After solving the elastic problem, one gets the horizontal displacement discontinuity $\boldsymbol{\delta u}^*(x)$ across the interface for each position x of the interface. Back to the temporal space, one gets a discontinuity

$$\boldsymbol{\delta u}(x) = \boldsymbol{\delta u}^*(x) \sin(\omega t) \quad (9)$$

and a velocity discontinuity

$$\delta \mathbf{v}(x) = \delta \mathbf{u}^*(x) \omega \cos(\omega t). \quad (10)$$

The tangential force $\boldsymbol{\tau}$, even though it was neglected while computing the elastic problem, can be approximated assuming a Coulombic friction. It then depends on the normal force magnitude $|\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n|$ as:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}(x) = \mu \cdot |\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n(x)| \left(\frac{\delta \mathbf{v}(x,y)}{|\delta \mathbf{v}(x,y)|} \right). \quad (11)$$

where μ is the friction coefficient that depends on temperature and was obtained using a friction setup at McGill University as described in appendix A. The parenthesis shows that the tangential force is always acting against slippage. $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n$ is obtained from the elastic problem as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n(x) = \sigma_{yy}^*(x) \sin(\omega t) \cdot \mathbf{e}_y \quad (12)$$

$\sigma_{yy}^*(x) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^*(x) \cdot \mathbf{e}_y \cdot \mathbf{e}_y$ being the vertical stress on the horizontal interface obtained by solving the normalized problem discussed in section 3.1. The average dissipated mechanical work associated to friction during an ultrasonic cycle therefore writes

$$\dot{Q}_{fric}(x) = \langle \boldsymbol{\tau} \cdot \delta \mathbf{v} \rangle \quad (13)$$

the operator $\langle \cdot \rangle$ being the average operator over an ultrasonic vibration period $2\pi/\omega$. Noting that

$$\left(\frac{\delta \mathbf{v}(x,y)}{|\delta \mathbf{v}(x,y)|} \right) \cdot \delta \mathbf{v} = |\delta \mathbf{v}(x,y)| \quad (14)$$

one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{Q}_{fric}(x) &= \alpha_h^2 \frac{\omega}{2\pi} \\ &\times \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{\omega}} \mu |\sigma_{yy}^*(x) \sin(\omega t)| \cdot |\delta \mathbf{u}^*(x) \omega \cos(\omega t)| dt \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where the hammering coefficient α_h accounts for the part of the cycle when contact is lost between the sonotrode and the sample. Developing leads to:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{Q}_{fric}(x) &= \alpha_h^2 \frac{\omega^2}{2\pi} \mu |\sigma_{yy}^*(x) \delta u^*(x)| \\ &\times \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{\omega}} |\sin(\omega t) \cos(\omega t)| dt \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

and finally

$$\dot{Q}_{fric}(x) = \alpha_h^2 \frac{\omega}{\pi} \mu |\sigma_{yy}^*(x) \delta u^*(x)|. \quad (17)$$

Note that this friction dissipated power is proportional to the vibration frequency ω . This is clearly related to the dry friction behavior assumed in eq. (11).

Table 1: Intimate contact parameters.

$a_0 [\mu\text{m}]$	0.2
$\frac{a_0}{b_0}$	1
$\frac{w_0}{b_0}$	0.7
w^*	1.7
a^*	8.5
$R_c = \frac{(a^*)^{\frac{1}{5}}}{w^*}$	0.9
$D_{ic0} = \frac{1}{w^*}$	0.588

3.2.2 Intimate contact evolution

When welding the composite plates, the quality of the contact between the tape and the energy director film evolves as the surface asperities get squeezed. During the last couple of decades, several models have been proposed to predict the evolution of this contact.

In the present study we make use of the Lee and Springer [12] model that aims at predicting the evolution the degree of intimate contact. It is a scalar defined as the contact area ratio and reaches 1 when full contact is obtained. The Lee and Springer model has been widely used in the literature [13, 14, 15, 16], and proved its efficiency. The model for D_{ic} writes [12, 13]:

$$D_{ic}(x) = \frac{1}{w^*} \times \left[1 + a^* \int_0^t \frac{P_{app}}{\eta(T(x))} \right]^{\frac{1}{5}} \quad (18)$$

where $w^* = 1 + w_0/b_0$ and $a^* = 5w^*(a_0/b_0)^2$ are geometric parameters related to the interface roughness, as defined in Lee and Springer [12]. Using contact surface profile measurements, a_0 can be obtained [17, 18]. Nonetheless the other parameters cannot be obtained. In this first model the parameters used are simply adapted from the literature and are given in table 1. P_{app} is approximated by the constant load applied on the interface or the sonotrode holding force divided by the sample area, and $\eta(T(x))$ is the viscosity of the roughness, that is taken as the pure matrix viscosity [18]. It follows an Arrhenius law

$$\eta(T) = A \times \exp\left(\frac{E_a}{RT [K]}\right) \quad (19)$$

where R is the gas constant. The viscosity versus temperature is measured experimentally using rheometer.

Figure 5: Logarithm of viscosity versus inverse of temperature.

The pre-exponential factor A and the free energy E_a are determined using a linear fit in the log-inverse graph plot (see figure 5). One obtains

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \exp(-14.14) = 7.23 \times 10^{-7} \text{ Pa.s} \\ E_a &= R \times 1.34 \times 10^4 = 111.7 \text{ kJ/mol} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Equations (18) and (19) give the evolution of D_{ic} through an ordinary differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial D_{ic}}{\partial t} = D_{ic}^{-4} \left(\frac{a_0}{b_0} \right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{w_0}{b_0}} \right)^4 \frac{P_{app}}{A} \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{T(x)}\right) \quad (21)$$

The bad contact at the interface results in a temperature gap at the interface. The thermal contact resistance leading to this gap decreases as the contact increases (as D_{ic} increases). In this study we propose to model this resistance using the relation proposed by Levy et al. [19, 18] linking this thermal contact resistance R_c and the degree of intimate contact D_{ic} . For each position of the interface it writes:

$$R_c(D_{ic}(x)) = D_{ic(t=0)} a_0 \left(\frac{1}{k D_{ic}^2(x)} + \frac{1 - D_{ic}(x)}{k_{air} D_{ic}(x)} + \frac{1}{k} \right). \quad (22)$$

k being the thermal conductivity of the matrix and k_{air} that of the air. We shall use $k_{air} = 0.03 \text{ W/mK}$.

Note that because the temperature is not continuous across the interface, the interfacial source \dot{Q}_{fric} is equally split on each side of the interface.

Figure 6: Elastic and Loss Moduli for PEI at high temperature measured at 10Hz.

3.2.3 Adhesion evolution

In order to predict the quality of adhesion one is interested in both modeling the intimate contact and the healing. In order to get a good adhesion, once intimate contact is achieved, one has to keep bond hot enough, for a sufficient duration, to ensure diffusion of the polymer macromolecules across the interface. Following the reptation theory by De - Gennes [20] one can define a reptation, time t_r that represents the time the macromolecule needs to fully change its configuration. t_r can be modeled using an Arrhenius law:

$$t_r = A_r \exp\left(\frac{E_a}{R.T [K]}\right). \quad (23)$$

The complex moduli at high temperature were measured at $f = 10 \text{ Hz}$ with a rheometer as shown on figure 6. Using the Cox-Merck principle Ferry [21], the characteristic time

$$t_r = \frac{1}{2\pi f} = 15.9 \text{ ms} \quad (24)$$

is deduced from this test. The two curves cross at temperature 281.5°C which is the relaxation temperature for this test. Using eq. (23), with the free energy E_a obtained above, one can finally determine the value

$$A_r = 4.71 \times 10^{-13} \text{ s} \quad (25)$$

Figure 7: Mesh over the computation domain.

Considering that once the macromolecule has fully diffused across the interface healing is complete, one can define a degree of healing D_h that follows:

$$\frac{\partial D_h}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{t_r(T)}. \quad (26)$$

Several authors [12, 22, 23] proposed a coupled model that ensures that only the surface already in intimate contact starts healing. Based on these models we introduce a new variable D_a , the degree of adhesion, that fulfills:

$$D_a = D_{ic} \times D_h \quad (27)$$

ensuring that only the fraction in intimate contact heals. $D_a(x)$ is computed for each position x of the interface using D_{ic} and D_h obtained by solving the ordinary differential equations (21) and (26).

3.3 Implementation

The model is solved with the finite element method using the commercial software COMSOL multi-physics. Thanks to the symmetries of the system, a quarter of the two dimensional geometry is simulated (see figure 7). It consists of half the upper composite plate and a quarter of the film. The quarter geometry is meshed with 5063 unstructured triangles with refinement along the interface. The unknown are (i) the displacement vector and (ii) the temperature in the whole domain, obtained by solving the elastic problem and the heat transfer using a quadratic interpolation; and (iii) the degree of intimate contact and (iv) the degree of healing at each node of the interface. The couplings are summarized on figure 8.

A backward Euler solver is used for the time integration. The resolution is stopped when the minimum temperature in the film exceeds $T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$ (which occurs before 0.5 s). The computation is performed on a desktop computer in less than 5 min.

Figure 8: The three physical problems to be solved and their couplings.

Table 2: Parameters used in the simulation.

α_h	hammering coefficient	0.21
ω	sonotrode pulsation	125000 rad.s ⁻¹
a	sonotrode amplitude	86.2 μm
t_{ramp}	time to establish vibration	50 ms
P_{app}	sonotrode holding pressure	1.55 MPa

Following the experimental procedure, at initial time $t = 0$, the total holding pressure P_{app} is applied. The amplitude $a(t)$ of the displacement imposed by the sonotrode on the upper part of the assembly then starts increasing. It is ramped from 0 at $t = 0$ to the nominal amplitude at time $t = t_{ramp}$. The reference case presented in Fernandez Villegas [1] is replicated. The parameters that were not given in the text are given in table 2.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Dissipated powers

Figure 9 shows the different powers dissipated in the system. It is obtained by integrating successively the visco-elastic dissipation \dot{Q}_{bulk} (eq. (7)), the friction dissipation \dot{Q}_{fric} (eq. (17)) and the sum of both (the *total dissipation*) over the domain.

Fernandez Villegas [1] measured the experimental power delivered by the ultrasonic apparatus P_{rig} . Because of several losses, amongst which:

- the generator efficiency itself
- acoustic losses

Figure 9: Total simulated dissipated powers and measured generator power versus time. The measured power [1] is multiplied by the efficiency $\chi = 13\%$ to represent the actual transmitted power.

- dissipation in the composite plates
- dissipation/damping in the rig

only a fraction of this delivered power is dissipated in the system. Considering a constant efficiency $\chi = 13\%$, the experimental dissipated power $P_{exp} = \chi \cdot P_{rig}$ fits well with the present predicted total dissipation. In figure 9 after the initial ramp that corresponds to the sonotrode amplitude increase, we notice a first peak around $t_{ramp} = 0.05$ s that is associated with the high initial friction dissipation. Note that the knowledge of the transient regime is very approximate so that a better matching of the very initial stage could be obtained by simply changing the amplitude ramp in something more realistic. Following that peak, adhesion starts, such that the friction dissipation quickly decreases, leading to a slight decrease of the total power. Around $t_{min} = 0.38$ s, accurately reproducing the experimental trend, the power reaches a minimum and then rises again.

4.2 Temperature predictions

Figure 10 presents the temperature along the center of the energy director film at four different characteristic times. Note that because of symmetry only a half of the interface is plotted and position 0 corresponds

Figure 10: Temperature predictions along the interface at four characteristic times.

Figure 11: Temperature and displacement fields at time $t = t_{ramp} = 0.05$ s. General view and closeup.

to the center of the film. At $t_{ramp} = 0.05$ s, the temperature simply shows a slight increase at the edge of the energy directors. This is explained by the slippage at the interface that is higher at the edge than at the center (as shown on figure 11). It induces a higher friction dissipation. Then, the temperature increases until about $t = 0.15$ s, when the hottest point (the edge) reaches the PEI glass transition temperature ($T_g = 215^\circ\text{C}$). Then the visco-elastic dissipated power drops (as shown on figure 9) as a larger part of the film reaches the glass transition temperature. Eventually, at time $t = 0.4$ s, the whole film reached the glass transition temperature and flow can occur, as observed experimentally by Fernandez Villegas [1].

Figure 12 presents the profile across the plate and the film at three different locations: in the middle of

Figure 12: Temperature prediction at $t = 0.04$ s across the assembly thickness at three locations: central symmetry, 3/4 and edge.

the sample, at three quarters and at the edge of the film. Once again, for symmetry reasons, only a quarter of the domain is considered. The temperatures are plotted at time $t = 0.4$ s. During this initial heating phase, one can notice a very local heating of the bond. That is very encouraging for an efficient welding without deconsolidation of the substrates. This was, once again, experimentally observed [1] during this initial heating phase. One should finally notice that the temperature in the middle of the film ($y = 0$) is higher than the temperature at the interfaces film/substrate ($y = 0.125$ mm), which shows that flow might occur before the interfaces reach T_g .

4.3 Adhesion evolution

Figure 13 shows the degree of adhesion along the film/substrate interface at different times. Because of the higher edge friction dissipation discussed in section 4.2, at time $t = 0.1$ s, adhesion starts at the edge (around 6 mm). This is confirmed by the weak adhesion observed experimentally at the edge by Fernandez Villegas [1] and shown on figure 14. Right after that, heating and adhesion increase everywhere in the interface. At time $t = 0.4$ s, the degree of adhesion is non negligible everywhere along the interface, which was also observed experimentally.

Figure 13: Predicted degree of adhesion at different times.

Figure 14: Energy director and bottom composite substrate for 100 ms vibration time [1].

5 Conclusion

Ultrasonic welding of Carbon/PEI composite was investigated. As previously observed experimentally, a neat PEI film at the interface between the two plates to be welded acts as an energy director. It allows a local heating and ensures a progressive adhesion of the two plates to be welded.

In the present work, a numerical multiphysical model gave a better insight of the leading physical phenomena occurring during the heating phase. The model consists of an elastic problem that predicts the effects of the ultrasonic vibration, a heat transfer problem that predict the temperature increase and a coupled bonding evolution problem at the interface that predicts the evolution of the adhesion.

The simulation aims at replicating the reference experiment given in Fernandez Villegas [1]. The results

confirms that the heating is mostly initiated by friction dissipation between the energy director film and the composite plates. Once adhesion increase, slippage is reduced and friction drops whereas visco-elastic dissipation takes over. The temperature at the interface progressively increases until it reaches the glass transition temperature. Then squeeze flow of the resin can start, the heating phase is finished.

The predicted dissipated power were compared with the experimental power delivered by the ultrasonic unit. A transmitted power of 13% of this machine power was found to accurately fit the predicted dissipated power at the interface.

The numerical simulation will further be used to investigate the effects of different process parameters on the welding.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank professor Pascal Hubert without whom this collaboration would not have been possible. The authors also acknowledge the help of Marcus Scaramanga with the design and manufacturing of the friction measurement apparatus.

References

- [1] I. Fernandez Villegas. In Situ Monitoring of Ultrasonic Welding of Thermoplastic Composites Through Power and Displacement Data. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite*, in press, 2013.
- [2] A. Benatar, R. V. Eswaran, and S. K. Nayar. Ultrasonic welding of thermoplastics in the near-field. *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 29(23):1689–1698, 1989.
- [3] Z. Zhang, X. Wang, Y. Luo, and L. Wang. Study on Heating Process of Ultrasonic Welding for Thermoplastics. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 25(5):647–654, 2009.
- [4] M. N. Tolunay, P. R. Dawson, and K. K. Wang. Heating and bonding mechanisms in ultrasonic welding of thermoplastics. *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 23(13):726–733, 1983.
- [5] A. Benatar and T. G. Gutowski. Ultrasonic Welding of PEEK Graphite APC-2 Composites. *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 29(23):1705–1721, 1989.
- [6] C. J. Nonhof and G. A. Luiten. Estimates for Process Conditions During the Ultrasonic Welding of Thermoplastics. *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 36(9):1177–1183, 1996.
- [7] X. Wang, J. Yan, R. Li, and S. Yang. FEM Investigation of the Temperature Field of Energy Director During Ultrasonic Welding of PEEK Composites. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 19(5):593–607, 2006.
- [8] K. S. Suresh, M. Roopa Rani, K. Prakasan, and R. Rudramoorthy. Modeling of temperature distribution in ultrasonic welding of thermoplastics for various joint designs. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 186(1-3):138–146, 2007.
- [9] A. Levy, S. Le Corre, A. Poitou, and E. Soccard. Ultrasonic Welding of Thermoplastic Composites, Modeling of the Process Using Time Homogenization. *International Journal for Multiscale Computational Engineering*, 9(1): 53–72, 2011.
- [10] A. Levy, S. Le Corre, N. Chevaugeron, and A. Poitou. A levelset based approach for the finite element simulation of a forming process involving multiphysics coupling : ultrasonic welding of thermoplastic composites. *European Journal of Mechanics - A/Solids*, 30(4):501–509, 2011.
- [11] A. Levy, S. Le Corre, and A. Poitou. Ultrasonic welding of thermoplastic composites: a numerical analysis at the mesoscopic scale relating processing parameters, flow of polymer, and quality of adhesion. *International Journal of Material Forming*, in press, 2012.
- [12] W. I. Lee and G. S. Springer. A model of the manufacturing process of thermoplastic matrix composites. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 21(11):1017–1055, 1987.
- [13] S. Mantell and G. Springer. Manufacturing process models for thermoplastic composites. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 26(16):2348–2377, 1992.
- [14] F. Sonmez and H. Hahn. Analysis of the on-line consolidation process in thermoplastic composite tape placement. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 10(6):543, 1997.
- [15] C. Ageorges, L. Ye, and M. Hou. Advances in Fusion Bonding Techniques for Joining Thermoplastic Matrix Composites: a Review. *Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing*, 32(6):839–857, 2001.
- [16] J.-F. Lamethe, P. Beauchene, and L. Leger. Polymer dynamics applied to PEEK matrix composite welding. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 9(3):233–240, 2005.
- [17] F. Yang and R. Pitchumani. A fractal Cantor set based description of interlaminar contact evolution during thermoplastic composites processing. *Journal of Materials Science*, 36(19):4661–4671, 2001.
- [18] A. Levy, D. Heider, J. Tierney, and J. Gillespie. Inter-layer Thermal Contact Resistance Evolution with the Degree of

- Intimate Contact in the Processing of Thermoplastic Composite Laminates. *Journal for Composite Materials*, (In press), 2013.
- [19] A. Levy, J. Tierney, D. Heider, J. W. Gillespie, P. Lefebure, and D. Lang. Modeling of Inter-Layer Thermal Contact Resistance During Thermoplastic Tape Placement. In *SAMPE 2012 - Baltimore*, 2012.
- [20] P. G. De - Gennes. Reptation of a polymer chain in the presence of fixed obstacles. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 55:572, 1971.
- [21] J. D. Ferry. *Viscoelastic Properties of Polymers*. John Wiley and Sons, 1980.
- [22] C. A. Butler, R. L. McCullough, R. Pitchumani, and J. W. Gillespie Jr. An analysis of mechanisms governing fusion bonding of thermoplastic composites. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 11(4):338, 1998.
- [23] F. Yang and R. Pitchumani. Nonisothermal healing and interlaminar bond strength evolution during thermoplastic matrix composites processing. *Polymer Composites*, 24(2): 263–278, 2003.
- [24] ASTM International. ASTM D1894 - 93. Standard Test Method for Static and Kinetic Coefficients of Friction of Plastic Film and Sheeting, 1995.
- [25] R. H. W. Thijs and R. Akkerman. Design of an experimental setup to measure tool-ply and ply-ply friction in thermoplastic laminates. *International Journal of Material Forming*, 2 (1):197–200, 2009.
- [26] G. Lebrun, M. N. Bureau, and J. Denault. Thermoforming-Stamping of Continuous Glass Fiber/Polypropylene Composites: Interlaminar and Tool-Laminate Shear Properties. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, 17(2):137–165, 2004.
- [27] J. Sun, M. Li, Y. Gu, D. Zhang, Y. Li, and Z. Zhang. Interply friction of carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg stacks under different processing conditions. *Journal of Composite Materials*, in press, 2013.

A Measurement of the friction coefficient

The classical coulomb law has been widely used to characterize composite friction behavior. It consists in considering a behavior such that a constant friction coefficient can be determined as:

$$f_c = \frac{T}{N} \quad (28)$$

Figure 15: Friction coefficient measurement setup.

where T is the tangent load and N is the normal load applied between the substrate and the film.

f_c is determined using a friction setup based on the ASTM method D1894 [24], initially developed for measuring thin plastic sheet friction coefficient. The setup is similar to the one proposed by Thijs and Akkerman [25], Lebrun et al. [26] or Sun et al. [27]. It consists of two platens that apply a controlled normal load and is positioned in an MTS machine (shown on figure 15). Two PEI films are attached on each platen, and a CF/PEI composite plate is compressed between those wrapped platens. The contact area is that of the platens: $50.8 \text{ mm} \times 101.6 \text{ mm}$. A normal load corresponding to 86 and 129 kPa is applied and the plate is pulled through, using the MTS tensile machine, at a constant velocity of 1.17 mm/s and 2.33 mm/s . The measured extraction force is averaged over steady state phase of the test, that is reached after around 20 mm. Using the two normal loads, two values of the friction coefficient are obtained for each velocity. The test is performed at room temperature. Results are given on table 3.

The friction coefficient obtained using the two different normal and two different velocities present less than 10% dispersion and show the adequacy of the coulomb law. An average of these four values is retained in the simulation. Note that we are mostly in-

Table 3: Friction coefficient measurements.

Velocity mm/s	Normal Force kPa	Friction coefficient
1.17	86	0.189
2.33	86	0.196
1.17	129	0.201
2.33	129	0.196
		$0.195 \pm 3\%$

terested in the room temperature behavior since the friction will mostly occur at the initial stage of the process, at low temperature.

B Determination of the viscoelastic modulus at high frequency

The elastic and loss moduli E' and E'' of the neat PEI were measured using a DMA apparatus between room temperature and 235°C for five frequencies f : 0.1, 1, 10 and 100Hz. Using a time temperature superposition principle, the obtained data were shifted onto the $f = 1\text{ Hz}$ master curve, assuming that:

$$E'(T, f) = E'(T + a(f \rightarrow 1), 1) \quad (29)$$

and

$$E''(T, f) = E''(T + a(f \rightarrow 1), 1). \quad (30)$$

The obtained shift factors a are plotted for each frequency on figure 16. Extrapolation of this shift factor to 20kHz gives:

$$a(20\text{kHz} \rightarrow 1\text{ Hz}) = -14.5^\circ\text{C} \quad (31)$$

and allows to predict the elastic and loss moduli of PEI at 20kHz, as shown on figure 17.

Figure 16: Obtained shift factor and its extrapolation to 20kHz.

Figure 17: Elastic and loss moduli of PEI measured at 1 Hz and shifted to 20kHz.